

Notes

Polarographic Behaviour of Molybdenum (VI) at Dropping Mercury Electrode in Potassium Chloride and Phosphoric Acid

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M. VON-STACKELBERG¹ found that molybdate does not produce a polarographic wave from neutral or alkaline solutions. The polarographic reduction of +6 molybdenum have been studied in sulphuric, hydrochloric, perchloric and phosphoric acids by Hoeltje and Geyer². Carritt³ investigated the polarographic behaviour of +6 and +3 molybdenum in various concentrations of sulphuric and hydrochloric acids. Molybdenum has also been found to produce a double wave with half-wave potentials of about -0.35 and -0.50 volts in nitric acid-ammonium nitrate containing lactic and oxalic acids⁴. Boltz *et al.*⁵ reported that molybdate present in a supporting electrolyte of pH 2.8 composed of 0.03M disodium hydrogen phosphate, 0.1M citric acid and 0.1M potassium chloride produces a well defined double wave. Mandelic acid (0.1M) and thymol (0.005%) have been also used as supporting electrolyte and maxima suppressor respectively, in studying the polarograms of +6 molybdenum⁶. Many other electrolytes have been tried for the study of the polarography of +6 molybdenum⁷⁻⁹.

According to Meites¹³ molybdenum is polarographically reduced in potassium chloride only in the presence of phosphoric acid. Polarographic study of a system consisting of H_2MoO_4 , H_3PO_4 and H_2O_2 have revealed the formation of phosphomolybdate complexes having molybdic to phosphoric acid ratios as 1:1 and 1:2 respectively. The formation constants of these complexes have also been reported.¹¹

In the course of their investigation of some complexes of +6 molybdenum the authors found it necessary to select suitable supporting electrolytes for the electroactive systems and also to confirm the above observations.

Experimental

Polarograms were obtained in the conventional manner using a recording type polarograph, PO_4

Radiometer Polariter. Purified hydrogen was passed through each solution to remove dissolved oxygen. The experimental conditions, as specified below were kept constant: damping—7, drop time (t)—2.8 sec per drop, temp.—21.5°, chart speed—2 cms per min, rate of flow of mercury from the dropping electrode (m)—2.12 mg per sec, and $m^{2/3}t^{1/6}$ —1.960.

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR quality. Hexavalent molybdenum was taken in the form of $Na_2MoO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$. A fresh solution of gelatine (0.01%) was used as maxima suppressor. Doubly distilled mercury was used as DME.

Discussion

The accompanying polarograms (Fig. 1a, 1b, 1c and 1d) show the reduction of +6 molybdenum in potassium chloride and phosphoric acid. The concentrations of +6 molybdenum and potassium chloride were kept constant while the concentration of phosphoric acid was changed as described. The polarograms exhibit two cathodic reversible waves for +6 molybdenum which result from its reduction to +5 and +3 states with half-wave potentials -0.58 and -0.90 volts respectively. The alternative possibility of its reduction to +4 molybdenum is unlikely as it contradicts the known electrochemical characteristics of molybdate solutions. In Fig. 1a the wave height of the first reduction step, +6 to +5, is very small, whereas in Fig. 1c the second stage of reduction, +5 to +3, is not satisfactory for the purpose of either qualitative or quantitative analysis. In Figs. 1b and 1d the two waves corresponding to the two reduction states are quite clear. In the latter case the wave of +6 molybdenum starts from -0.40 volts. As already reported¹² by the authors, varying the concentration of phosphoric acid even upto four times the concentration of molybdate does not result in any shift in the $E_{1/2}$ values of molybdate.

Fig. 1. Molybdenum waves in solns. containing 1.0M KCl, 0.0025M sod. molybdate and (a) 0.0050M, (b) 0.0075M, (c) 0.01M, (d) 0.0075M H_3PO_4 .

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Studies in Pyridothiazolopyrimidines and Pyridopyrimidothiazines

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SYNTHESIS of thiazoloquinazolines has been reported by the condensation of anthranilic acid with 2-Chloro thiazoles¹ and with allyl isothiocyanates². Attempts made for the synthesis of I on the same lines by the condensation of 2-amino nicotinic acid with 2-chlorothiazoles and allyl isothiocyanates were unsuccessful. The failure may be attributed to the less basic nature of amino group in 2-amino nicotinic acid. Synthesis of I has, however, been achieved by the condensation of 2-chloro nicotinic acid with 2-amino-4-aryl thiazoles. The chlorine here being hedged between two electron withdrawing groups should be more reactive. The yields of the products, however, remained very poor. It may be due to the lack of requisite basicity of amino group in 2-amino-4-arylthiazoles.

Similarly condensation of 2-chloro-4 : 6-dimethyl-5-nitro-nicotinitrile (III) have been carried out with 2-amino-4-aryl thiazoles IV to furnish I.

Condensation of III with 2-thio-4 : 4 : 6-trialkyl-1 : 4-dihydropyrimidine furnished 2 : 2 : 4-trialkyl-7 : 9-dimethyl-8-nitro-2H, 6H-pyrido (3,2-a) pyrimido (2,1-b) (1,3)thiazin-6-one (II).

Experimental

6 : 8-Dimethyl-7-nitro-3-phenyl-5H-pyrido(2,3-d) thiazolo(3,2-a) pyrimidin-5-one (Ia) :

A mixture of 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole³ (1.76 g, 0.01 mole) and 2-chloro-4 : 6-dimethyl-5-nitro nicotinic acid⁴⁻⁶ (2.3 g, 0.01 mole) was heated at 140°-50° for half an hour and the temperature was gradually raised to 180°-90° where it was maintained for half an hour. The solid mass was treated with sodium carbonate solution (10%), filtered and the residue was washed with water and then treated with ethanol (10 ml) and filtered again. The ethanolic filtrate on dilution with water furnished a compound (1 g) which after crystallisation was found to be 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole, m.p. 150°. The ethanol insoluble product on crystallisation from dioxan gave (Ia) 0.43 g. in 15% yield, m.p. 221°. Found : N, 15.64. C₁₇H₁₂N₄SO₃ requires, N, 15.90%. Ib m.p. 180°, yield 12%, Found : C, 58.78; H, 2.45; N, 14.28%. C₁₇H₁₁ClN₄SO₃ requires, C, 58.84; H, 2.84; N, 14.54%. I.R. 1620 (>C=N-), 1680 (amidic keto) and 1580 cm⁻¹ (due to a combination of C, N and S⁷). Ic, m.p. 208°, yield 14%, Found : N, 15.50; C₁₈H₁₄N₄SO₃ requires, N, 15.30%. Id m.p. 210°-11°, yield 40%. Found : N, 15.87; C₁₆H₁₈N₅SO₄ requires, N, 16.24%.

2 : 2 : 4 : 7 : 9-Penta methyl-8-nitro-2H,-6H-pyrido(3,2-e) pyrimido (2,1-b) (1,3) thiazin-6-one (IIa).

2-Chloro-4 : 6-dimethyl-5-nitro nicotinic acid (2.3 g, 0.01 mole) and 2-thio-4 : 4 : 6-trimethyl-1 : 4-dihydropyrimidine⁸ (1.56 g, 0.01 mole) were heated together in an oil bath at 160° for 3 hr. The resulting product (IIa) was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 240°. Found : N, 16.44; C₁₆H₁₆N₄SO₃ requires, N, 16.80%. IIb, m.p. 230°. Found : N, 15.57; C₁₆H₁₈N₄SO₃ requires, N, 15.55%.

Fig. I. (III, Y = COOH) Ia, X = O, R = H
 Ib, X = O, R = Cl
 Ic, X = O, R = CH₃
 Id, X = NH, R = OC₂H₅
 HCl
 (III, Y = CN),

Fig. II. IIa, R = CH₃
 IIb, R = C₂H₅